

THE INFLUENCE OF PRE-TENSION LOAD IN THE COMPOSITE LAMINATE FASTENER JOINT DURING REPEATED TIGHTENING

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ABSTRACT

Bolted joint is commonly used on carbon fiber reinforced polymer composite structures due to its reliability. In the actual assembly work, one fastener is only required to be installed once. One reason is the pre-tension load of the fastener is decreased with the time increase of tighten and loosen operation. In this paper, the relationship between tightening torque and pre-load during repeated assembly has been studied.

Based on Schatz-Analyse test simulation system, the pre-tension load of a protruding tension head titanium hex-drive bolt used in a carbon fiber reinforced composite joint under 70% of the given installation tightening torque has been measured. Accordingly, the friction coefficients of bearing surface and thread have been calculated. In the experiment, for the fastener, different diameter (-10 and -16) and types of collar have been studied. For the composite panels, 13 types of common used surface finish have been studied. For -10 fastener, 15 times of repeated installation operation have been performed (one installation cycle means a complete tightening and loosening operation), while for -16 fastener, 3 times have been performed.

The experimental results show that the pre-tension load decreases with the increase of the repeated installation times. The equivalent total friction coefficient, which includes the friction coefficient of the thread and the friction coefficient of the bearing surface under nut, increases with the number of repeated installation. The friction coefficient depends on thread lubrication and bearing surface state under nut. In most of the cases, the increase of the bearing surface friction coefficient is more significant than the increase of the thread friction coefficient. Therefore, it is recommended that the bearing surface status should be properly re-established whenever the surface is used more than once, and the fastener should be replaced when it has been used.

1 INTRODUCTION

In a bolted joint, the common installation procedure is tightening the nut while keeping the bolt fixed. The nut will overcome its own anti-loose locking torque, thread friction torque and friction torque between the nut and the bearing surface to achieve the installation, resulting in pre-tension load in the bolt and clamping force to the joint panels. The pre-tension load is important to the joint mechanical and functional performance, for example, fatigue and fuel sealing, etc.

- a) The clamping force produces friction between the bearing surfaces of bolted structures, which reduces fastener transferred load and the bearing load on the fastener hole. Therefore, the joint strength is increase, especially in the composite structure joints which is clearance fit installation.
- b) For the metallic joint, the clamping force also can significantly improve the fatigue performance.
- c) The preload can arrest the delamination expansion caused by the edge impact, which increases the structural damage tolerance and safety characteristics.
- d) The preload can improve the sealing performance of the tank area.

- e) High preload can improve the boundary support coefficients, which improves structural stability performance.

The appropriate preload on the bolted structure can improve its static strength and fatigue strength, but due to the poor out-of-plane strength of composite structure, too high preload will lead to the following two issues:

- a) Excessive preload may cause the bolt or nut thread to enter a plastic deformation, which may cause fastener static failure or fatigue failure under larger external loads or repeated fatigue loads.
- b) The poor out-of-plane strength of the composite material limits the maximum preload force that can be achieved by the bolts. The excessive preload force may cause resin collapse.

Therefore, during bolt installation, the preload should be controlled properly. The preload of most of bolts is controlled by the wrench torque.

But not all of the tightening torque is converted to preload, in fact, only about 10% of tightening torque converts to preload, while the other about 90% of the tightening torque used to overcome the friction, including approximately 40% thread friction and 50% bearing surface friction as shown in Figure 1. In the actual bolted joint, these ratios are changed due to the influence of geometrical parameters, lubrication state, structural surface finish or coatings etc. In this paper, the relationship between the tightening torque and the pre-tension load under repeated installation is studied, and different bolt diameters and bearing surface finishes are taken into account.

Figure 1: Tightening torque distribution.

Mainly include the following:

- a) Total friction coefficient shows the relationship between the total tightening torque and the preload.
- b) Thread friction coefficient shows the relationship between thread torque and preload
- c) Bearing surface friction coefficient shows the relationship between the bearing surface torque and the preload.

In the actual fastener assembly work, the same fastening connection structure may be repeatedly tightened and loosened, taking into account the need for maintenance of the parts. This test is used to analyze the relationship between the preload and tightening torque during repeated tightening, to guide the field maintenance of the torque control.

2 TEST EQUIPMENT AND PRINCIPLES

This test is based on Schatz-Analyse test simulation system, which contains tightening gun, mechanical arm, torque / angle sensor, torque / clamping force sensor, data acquisition unit, measuring software and etc.

3 DATA PROCESSING

In this experiment, the parameters such as tightening torque and preload are measured directly, and the friction coefficients of the bolt joint are calculated, so as to analyze the relationship between tightening torque and preload. The parameters involved in this test are as follows.

3.1 Preload coefficient K

Preload coefficient K is related to wrench torque and preload, the equation is as follow:

$$K = \frac{T}{Fd} \quad (1)$$

Where:

T is wrench torque, unit is Nm

F is pre-tension load, unit is N

d is inside diameter of nut bearing area, unit is mm.

3.2 Total friction coefficient μ_{tot}

The equation of total friction coefficient μ_{tot} is as follow:

$$\mu_{tot} = \frac{\frac{T}{F} - \frac{P}{2\pi}}{0.577d_2 + 0.5D_b} \quad (2)$$

Where: T is wrench torque, unit is Nm

P is tread pitch, unit is mm

F is preload, unit is N

d_2 is normal diameter of tread, unit is mm

D_b is the efficient friction diameter of the bearing surface, unit is mm.

The total friction coefficient is only used to give a cooperation of the bolt joints under different friction conditions, whose formula is premised on the assumption that the thread friction coefficient is the same as the bearing surface friction coefficient.

3.3 Thread friction coefficient μ_{th}

The equation of thread friction coefficient μ_{th} is as follow:

$$\mu_{th} = \frac{\frac{T_{th}}{F} - \frac{P}{2\pi}}{0.577d_2} \quad (3)$$

Where: T_{th} is thread torque, unit is Nm

P is thread pitch, unit is mm

F is preload, unit is N

d_2 is normal diameter of tread, unit is mm.

3.4 Bearing surface friction coefficient μ_b

The equation of Bearing surface friction coefficient μ_b is as follow:

$$\mu_b = \frac{T_b}{0.5D_b F} \quad (4)$$

Where: T_b is bearing surface torque, unit Nm

D_b is the efficient friction diameter of the bearing surface, unit is mm.

F is preload, unit is N.

4 Test results

4.1 Detailed results for one -12 and one -16 protruding tension head titanium hex-drive bolt

Figure 2 provides 15 pre-tension load results of 15 times repeated installation operation for a protruding tension head titanium hex-drive bolt used in a carbon fiber reinforced composite joint under the same tightening torque at fastening speed 20 r / min.

Figure 2: pre-tension load results of 15 times repeat installation operation for one -12 fastener under the same tightening torque and fastening speed

From Figure 2, it can be seen that, under the same tightening torque, with the increase of the tightening times, the pre-tension load is gradually reduced. When the 15th installation is carried out, the pre-tension load is attenuated by 43.7% compared to the first time.

It can be seen from Fig. 3 that the equivalent total friction coefficient, the friction coefficient of the thread and the friction coefficient of the bearing surface increase with the increase of the number of tightening. The increase of the friction coefficient of the bearing surface is the largest, whose increase ratio is 168%, while the friction coefficient of the thread has an increase of 34.5%. The change in friction coefficient depends on the change in the friction surface state. It can be considered that, the bearing surface is damaged more serious than the thread. And the weight ratio is about 5/6 for the bearing surface while it is 1/6 for the thread. It is important to note that the weight ration of the friction coefficient for all of the test pieces is not the same, which depends on the physical properties of the bearing surface, such as hardness, brittleness, roughness and so on.

It can be seen from Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 that the test torque becomes unstable with the increase of the number of tightening times before the test torque reaches the peak value.

Figure 3: 15 friction coefficient of 15 times repeated installation operation for one -12 fastener under the same tightening torque and fastening speed

Figure 4: The relationship between pre-tension load and tightening torque for the first tightening operation of one -12 fastener

Figure 5: The relationship between pre-tension load and tightening torque for the 15th tightening operation of one -12 fastener

Figure 6 provides pre-tension load results of 3 times repeated installation operation for another protruding tension head titanium hex-drive bolt used in a carbon fiber reinforced composite joint, whose dash no. is -16, under the same tightening torque and fastening speed.

Figure 6: 3 pre-tension load results of 3 times repeated installation operation for one -16 fastener under the same tightening torque and fastening speed

From Figure 6, it can be seen that, under the same tightening torque, with the increase of the tightening times, the pre-tension load is gradually reduced. When the third installation is carried out, the pre-tension load is attenuated by 43.7% to the first time.

At the same time, it can be seen from Fig.7 that the increase ratio for the friction coefficient of the bearing surface under nut increases is 193%, while the friction coefficient of thread increases from has an increase ratio of 137%.

Figure 7: friction coefficient of 3 times repeated installation operation for one -16 fastener under the same tightening torque and fastening speed

Figure 8: The relationship between pre-tension load and tightening torque for the first tightening operation of one -16 fastener

Figure 9: The relationship between pre-tension load and tightening torque for the third tightening operation of one -16 fastener

In addition to these two test pieces, all the other test pieces have a similar test results. With the increase of the tightening number, the friction coefficient of the bearing surface, the thread and the equivalent total friction coefficient increase. The resulting preload is gradually reduced and the attenuation of the preload is gradually reduced.

4.2 Different results for tension collar and shear collar

In this chapter, the results of different types of collars, which includes tension collar and shear collar have been studied.

Figure 10 and Figure 11 present the pre-tension load results and friction coefficients of three types of collars assembled the same bolt, the bearing surface is the one next to the tooling. The tightening torque is the same. It can be seen that the tendency of the pre-tension load and friction coefficients for different types of collars is the same.

Figure 10: pre-tension load results of 15 times repeated installation operation for three types of collars assembled the same bolt, the bearing surface is the one next to the tooling

Figure 11: friction coefficient of 15 times repeated installation operation for three types of collars assembled the same bolt, the bearing surface is the one next to the tooling

Figure 12 and Figure 13 present the pre-tension load results and friction coefficients of three types of collars assembled the same bolt, the bearing surface is the one next to the vacuum bag. The tightening torque of tension collar and shear collar is the same. It can be seen that the tendency of the pre-tension load and friction coefficients for different types of collars is the same.

Figure 12: pre-tension load results of 15 times repeated installation operation for three types of collars assembled the same bolt, the bearing surface is the one next to the vacuum bag.

Figure 13: friction coefficient of 15 times repeated installation operation for three types of collars assembled the same bolt, the bearing surface is the one next to the vacuum bag.

4.3 Different results for tension collar and shear collar

In this chapter, the results of different types of surface finish status have been studied.

Figure 14 presents the pre-tension load results of 13 types of bearing surface finish status, which include surface next to the tooling, surface next to the vacuum bag and different surface treatments for two surfaces of one composite panel. The fastener and the collar are the same. It can be seen that the tendency of the pre-tension load for different types of surface status is the same, while for some ones, the decay's speeds are quicker, and some ones are slower.

Figure 14: pre-tension load results of 15 times repeated installation operation for 13 types of bearing surface finish status

5 CONCLUSIONS

In summary, there is a certain relationship between the pre-tension load and the times of repeated installation numbers. The rules are as follows:

- a) The pre-tension load decays with the increase in the number of repeated installation.
- b) The pre-tension loads are different for different types of collars.
- c) The pre-tension load for the bearing surface next to tooling is bigger than the one for the bearing surface to the vacuum bag,
- d) Different surface treatments have different friction coefficients, which lead to different pre-tension load.

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